

Hegemony in Eurasia, the Joining of the Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific, and the Enduring Relevance of Mackinder's Heartland Theory

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Introduction

Theories in International Relations (I.R.) are necessarily subject to perfidious favour in the academy. Rarely, however, have theories been in vogue and then so maligned as those of British geographer Halford J. Mackinder. At the end of his illustrious career, he received the Charles P. Daley medal from the American Geographical Society, in 1944, in London, where he was praised by the U.S. ambassador as 'the first who fully enlisted geography as an aid to statecraft' (Sempa, 2015). Only a few years later, Mackinder's theories were libellously rubbished in the West for their supposed association with Nazi geopolitics and racial superiority. By the 1990s, they had fallen from favour completely in Europe and, to a lesser extent, the United States (U.S.).

Today, Mackinder's theories are experiencing a renaissance. Why? One answer is found in the parsimonious explanatory power of his theories that clearly illustrate not just how, but why, great power rivalry is engendered and the nodal security partnerships that may emanate from that. A longer answer is found in Mackinder's identification of Central Eurasia as the critical 'pivot area' that shapes global distributions of power. As such, it seems most appropriate to apply his ideas in the context of current geopolitical competition and rising polarity in the international system. In doing so, this article explains the contemporary formation of counterbalancing coalitions connecting the Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific regions and explores the geostrategic roles of smaller states in shaping these dynamics.

In addition to identifying Central Eurasia as pivotal, Mackinder also emphasized the strategic importance of the North Atlantic – or 'Midland Ocean' – as a historical hinge between the Old and New Worlds. Today, as wealth and power shift eastward, the Indo-Pacific has emerged as the primary geopolitical centre of gravity (Cannon and Hakata, 2022). Nevertheless, Mackinder's insights remain highly relevant: the Euro-Atlantic still serves as a vital balancing platform linking Europe and North America to Indo-Pacific security dynamics. Despite technological transformations, geography – and the ability to control or overcome it – continues to define the players, stakes, and measures of security in international relations (Gray, 1996).

The article proceeds as follows. The next section reassesses Mackinder's Heartland theory, its subsequent refinements, and his enduring relevance to international security today. The third section explores the centrality of geography to power in world politics, contrasting Mackinder's framework with mainstream I.R. theories. The fourth section examines hegemony and counter-hegemony dynamics in Eurasia, with a particular focus on China and Russia. The penultimate section analyses the geostrategic role of island and peripheral states as 'corks in the bottle' that constrain Eurasian hegemonic expansion. The article concludes with reflections on the continuing applicability of Mackinder's theories in a global order increasingly shaped by geopolitical competition across Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific.

Mackinder's enduring relevance

Mackinder delivered his landmark address identifying Central Eurasia as the geopolitical 'pivot area' of global power to the Royal Geographical Society in 1904. It laid the foundation for classical geopolitics, which examines how geographic factors such as location, control, resources, and physical terrain shape power dynamics and influence the strategies and behaviour of states. For Mackinder, the pivot area covered roughly today's five Central Asian states, as well as Afghanistan, much of Iran and the Caucasus region, and Russia from the Volga basin to Western China and northward to Lake Baikal and the Arctic Sea. After the First World War, however, Mackinder (1919) expanded the pivot area, which he now termed the 'Heartland', westward to include most of Eastern Europe, helping explain why his 1919 map differs from the 1904 graphic often reproduced in textbooks (see Maps 1 and 2). Nevertheless, Mackinder's core premise remained unchanged: control of the pivot area/Heartland would give an aspirant hegemon dominance of Eurasia and, eventually, Africa (the World-island) and thus the key to achieving global supremacy. Mackinder (1919, 261) wrote:

*Who rules East Europe commands the Heartland;
Who rules the heartland commands the World-island;
Who rules the World-island commands the World.*

If Mackinder clearly saw the danger posed to international distributions of power by unchecked hegemony in Eurasia, he also saw the 'way out'. Today, with the rise of China in Central Asia and the Western Pacific, the creation of the 'free and open Indo-Pacific' strategy designed to thwart Eurasian hegemony, and the growing networked security web spanning the Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific around the rim of Eurasia (see Cannon, 2025; Grgić and Wilkins, 2025; Cannon and Rossiter, 2025), we can clearly trace the enduring importance of Eurasia in global power dynamics – a core emphasis of Mackinder's theories. This is because

Mackinder's admittedly parsimonious theoretical framework effectively explains geopolitical dynamics in a globalized world over the *longue durée*.

Map 1: Image of Mackinder's 'Pivot Area', which largely corresponds to his 'Heartland'. Halford J. Mackinder, 'The Geographical Pivot of History', *Geographical Journal* 23 (4), April 1904, p.435. Originally from nl.wikipedia. Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=1626595>

Despite their explanatory power throughout the twentieth century and into the present day, Mackinder and his theories have attracted a fair number of detractors. Much of this criticism stems from German National Socialism (Nazism), with its emphasis on racial superiority and *Lebensraum*, the latter of which shared broadly similar elements with Mackinder's work. The unfortunate, incorrect, and libellous conflation of two separate strands of geopolitics led to the rubbishing of Mackinder and his theories in the West, particularly in Europe, for decades (Dodds and Woon, 2010). This confusion was exacerbated by Germany geographer and Nazi supporter, Karl Haushofer's explicit borrowing of Mackinder's Heartland theory, which he reinterpreted to justify Germany's violent continental ambitions (Herwig, 1999). Where Mackinder's theory was largely defensive, analytic, and cautionary, Haushofer's adaptation was normative, programmatic, and firmly expansionist, fitted to Nazi theories of racial superiority and global domination. Despite later attempts to link Mackinder directly to Haushofer's theory of *Geopolitik*, there is no evidence that Mackinder supported, collaborated

with, or was even aware of Haushofer's ideological appropriation of his work (Knutsen, 2014).¹

Map 2: By Halford Mackinder - Democratic Ideals and Reality, 1919
Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=23249132>

Many also criticise Mackinder for being Eurocentric and an inveterate British imperialist (O'Tuathail, 1994; Kearns, 2006). Yet discarding Mackinder's theories along with his political views would be shortsighted. It is difficult to separate individuals from the social and political contexts of their time. Few in London in 1904 (or 1942 amid global war centred on Eurasia) saw Mackinder's emphasis on Eurasia as the world's geopolitical fulcrum as problematic, though many today would rightly challenge its narrowness and its neglect of what is now termed the 'Global South'. But we live in a fundamentally changed world. As such, Mackinder as a geographer and theorist may not be in vogue everywhere, but his core insight – that a state's geography shapes its political power – remains highly instructive and illustrative. For him, political power was the product of strategic and economic geographic conditions as well as human capital and the ability of peoples to efficiently turn resources into national power (Mackinder, 1919). It is difficult to argue against this even in today's world. As C.S. Lewis (1966, pp.207-208) warned, 'chronological snobbery' – the uncritical acceptance of the intellectual assumptions of our own age – can obscure the enduring value

¹ Haushofer, despite initially being a mentor of both Adolf Hitler and Rudolf Hess, fell from Nazi favour when he criticized them for breaking the Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact when Germany invaded the Soviet Union in 1941 (Knutsen, 2014, p.848).

of earlier insights. Mackinder's work, despite its historical baggage, continues to offer essential lessons about the persistent role of geography in world politics.

Despite falling from grace, Mackinder's emphasis on geography as a determinant of technological deployment and power resonates strongly in the ongoing technological supremacy contest between China and the United States, as well as in the nodal security arrangements dotting the rim of Eurasia from Northwestern Europe through South and Southeast Asia and upwards to Northeast Asia (Simón, Lanoszka and Meijer, 2021). Moreover, his concerns about the dangers of unchecked Eurasian hegemony remain valid, particularly regarding their implications for – and potential causation of – contemporary strategic alignments and conflicts. Given the current flux centred on Eurasia, Mackinder's theoretical legacy deserves renewed reassessment.

Centrality of geography and power

If Mackinder's theories have a 'bottom line,' it is that geographic control and the power that accrues therefrom are enduring factors in global politics. This differentiates it from power-based theories such as realism and liberalism that have shaped much of our analysis of international politics since the early 20th century (Morgenthau, 1948; Waltz, 2018; Ikenberry, 2019). It does not, however, mean that Mackinder eschewed the quest for security, and thus, power by states. Instead, he saw that territorial control or the attempt to achieve it by force – the causal factor in interstate warfare – is a more constant variable than power. Nevertheless, the two are intrinsically connected and our world today clearly illustrates this, from Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022 (preceded by land grabs in Crimea and the Donbas in 2014) to China's island-building in the South China Sea.

Mackinder intrinsically understood why states can choose to act in, at times, terrifying and violent ways: *terra firma* matters. His theories underscore why states continue to vie for control over land, resources, and strategic islands. Territorial control remains the prime determinants of a state's power. Without territory and sovereignty, a state has none. Ask Poland or Uzbekistan or Azerbaijan, all of which have 'disappeared' from our maps over the years as Russia has usurped both.

Land has always been fundamental to human survival and resources key to civilizations' flourishing. We can live long-term neither in the air nor in the oceans despite stunning technological transformations. As such, geography forms a useful metric with which to theorize why states act the way they do. Mackinder noted: '... the geographical quantities in the calculation are more measurable and more nearly constant than the human' (Mackinder, 1904, p.437). Taking this as a starting point and using a *longue durée* perspective, Mackinder

(1904) posited that geographic control, and the resources (or power) that accrue therefrom, matter a great deal in terms of which empire, state, or people were ascendent. Because these factors mattered as much in 500 BC, 1500 AD, and 1904, Mackinder understood that they would continue to matter in the future, particularly as transformative technologies such as the railroad (in his day) tied the fates of states and empires together. Yet he cautioned that technology is merely a multiplier; the decisive variable is the fusion of mobility with the Heartland's resource self-sufficiency – food, fuel, metals – conditions that would allow a power to resist blockade and project force outward (Mackinder 1904, 1919). He stated: 'The actual balance of political power at any given time is, of course, the product, on the one hand, of geographical conditions, both economic and strategic, and, on the other hand, of the relative number, virility, equipment, and organization of the competing peoples' (Mackinder, 1904, p.437).

If we take this broad maxim as valid, it means that a state with a certain amount of territory (and the national power accrued therefrom) may not only push back against its attempted subordination but forge a nation or empire in the process. History is replete with examples: Rome's struggle against Carthage's superior power was the crucible in which the Roman Empire was forged. Arab conquests in Iberia birthed not only today's Spain and Portugal but created the first global empires via their seafaring explorations that bypassed the Mediterranean – then a 'Muslim Lake' – to the Indies (Crowley, 2015). The influx of Aztec gold and Inca silver boosted Spanish power, weakened the Ottomans, and inadvertently spurred the rise of Atlantic-facing empires like England, the Netherlands, and France. Japan's emergence stemmed from an abrupt end to isolation forced by an industrializing U.S., prompting Tokyo's regional assertion to resist Western imperialism. Similarly, Russia achieved superpower status (as the Soviet Union) only after overcoming Germany's 1941 invasion in the Second World War. Subsequently, Soviet expansion was checked by a U.S.-led coalition, resulting in alliances such as NATO, the FVEYs intelligence-sharing group of Anglophone states, and America's extensive hub-and-spoke alliances in the Western and South Pacific.

One benefit of Mackinder's emphasis on geography is its tangible nature. Territory has physical resources, including populations, essential for survival and prosperity. Thus, territory and sovereignty over it are inherent national interests worth defending. Conversely, power – unlike geography – can be measured variably, often with deficiencies (Kadera and Sorokin, 2004; Barnett and Duvall, 2009; Donelli and Cannon, 2023). Although widely desired, the reasons behind its pursuit often enter philosophical or metaphysical realms. Not everyone seeks power; some prioritize comfort or approval. By focusing exclusively on power as the primary variable in I.R. theory, we risk sidelining classical geopoliticians like Mackinder and Dutch-American political scientist, Nicholas J. Spykman.

Mackinder's insights remain relevant today, demonstrating geography's enduring role in global politics. While territory and sovereignty continue to underpin power and security, not all geography holds equal strategic value. Certain regions, peninsulas, island chains, and straits inherently matter more, underscoring Mackinder's enduring relevance in contemporary international relations. Eurasia, in particular, has historically been the focal point of global power struggles (Rasler and Thompson, 2014). Mackinder's heartland theory clearly identifies it as the crucible in which global balances of power are determined.

In this, Mackinder saw the importance not just of territorial control, but of the resources that come from it. Should those resources be maximally utilized – to produce technologies like the railroad and telegraph in Mackinder's day – it would grant the actor (Russia, Britain, or another power) the ability to achieve full sovereignty over its territory and more effectively contest the sovereignty of neighbours. This phenomenon is hardly unique to Eurasia: the Inca mobilized their resources to build an extensive road network, expanding into surrounding regions via conquest (Hyslop, 1994); Rome did so with its own roads (Ando, 2017). Neither contested global hegemony, however, in part because the 'global' age began with Europeans heading west and south across the Atlantic – a response to mounting pressure from Asia Minor that shut the doors to Mediterranean trade and routes east.

Mackinder, a geographer with a keen knowledge of history, recognized the enduring primacy of Eurasia in shaping global outcomes. He asked: 'I ask you, therefore, for a moment to look upon Europe and European history as subordinate to Asia and Asiatic history, for European civilization is, in a very real sense, the outcome of the secular struggle against Asiatic invasion' (Mackinder, 1904, p.423). In his view, successive waves of nomadic incursions from the East – Goths, Huns, Mongols, Turks – were the crucible in which Europe itself was forged. Because of Eurasia's outsized influence on global power balances, Mackinder argued that Britain, as a maritime power, could not allow a single 'World-island' hegemon to dominate Eurasia's vast resources and newly emergent rail-based connectivity.

By identifying Eurasia as the decisive theatre of world affairs, Mackinder's work highlights how geography can magnify or diminish a state's power. His World-island thesis underscores that control of Eurasian resources – especially through modern technological advances – can give an ascendant power a genuine path to global dominance. From Mackinder's era to the present, events in Eastern Europe, Central Asia, and the broader Eurasian rim illustrate his enduring influence on how we conceive of strategic competition and the centrality of territory. The super-continent has also historically been the focal point of global power struggles, which have burst forth into global wars – from the Seven Years' War to the Napoleonic Era to the First, Second and Cold Wars (Rasler and Thompson, 2014).

Heartland theory and beyond

According to Mackinder's famous dictum, referenced above, Eastern Europe plays a privileged role as the gateway to Inner Eurasia and underscores its enduring geostrategic importance. Control offers the controller not only vast resources but also significant defensive/offensive and logistical advantages, and has made it a persistent focus for great power rivalry for centuries: Russian/Ottoman, German/Russian etc. This relevance is starkly reflected in contemporary geopolitics, such as Russia's ongoing efforts to subsume Ukraine and Europe's concerns about the viability of its eastern flank (concerns that were mirrored in Moscow and precipitated its invasion in 2022).

Mackinder also anticipated the destabilizing effects of alliances among Eurasian powers, warning that a coalition like that of Germany and Russia could disrupt both Eurasian and, eventually, global power balances. Such an eventuality is more likely today as Russia and China, for their own national interests, have become increasingly close to keep external powers out of Central Eurasia and potentially reshape the international order.

What concerned Mackinder most in his day was Imperial Russia, particularly its expanding railway networks and reach. For him the railroad was revolutionary because, by granting continental mobility, it negated sea-power barriers (Mackinder, 1904). Mackinder, as a geographer, knew less about the natural resources with which the pivot area is imbued than we do today. He was, nevertheless, correct to highlight the wealth of resources and the territory itself as power generators. The Russians had the option of withdrawing from Moscow in both the French invasion in 1812 and the German invasion in 1941, regrouping, resupplying, and eventually pushing both out. What Russia did afterwards in both cases also aligns with Mackinder's premise: it expanded into the peripheral lands of Eurasia – particularly Eastern Europe – and became a major power in the post-1815 Concert of Europe, and a superpower that contested world hegemony for nearly 50 years post-1945. From this position, Mackinder presciently foresaw, Russia would be formidable. However, Mackinder also recognized the possibility of another power, such as Germany or a coalition of Eurasian states, challenging this dominance. In particular, his classical geopolitical theory foresaw China potentially surpassing Russia's influence in Eurasia and gaining '... an oceanic frontage to the resources of the great continent, an advantage as yet denied to the Russian tenant of the pivot region' (Mackinder, 1904, p.437). This, he argued, would be the greatest threat, enabling China to contest maritime supremacy.

States that attempt to gain hegemony of the World-island, however, should expect opposition, according to Mackinder. In fact, his statement about Russia ends this way: 'She [Russia] can strike on all sides and *be struck from all sides, save the north*' (Mackinder, 1904, p.436 [my

emphasis]). In short, balancing coalitions will emerge in and around Eurasia to counter hegemonic attempts in the Heartland. China should expect this, too.

Mackinder was a visionary in numerous other ways. Crucially, he foresaw the decisive role of an off-shore maritime balancer – once Britain, now the U.S. – in marshalling rimland coalitions and projecting naval power into the marginal seas to block a Heartland hegemonic contender (Mackinder 1904, 1919). He would later enlarge his framework to argue that air-power could vault sea barriers more easily than fleets and thereby shrink distance. The advent of long-range strike aircraft, UAVs, and global ISR networks, among others, only intensifies the relevance of his vision.

Hegemony and counter-hegemony in Eurasia today

While one can criticize Mackinder's deterministic retelling of Europe's rise, his parsimonious theory retains explanatory power and remains highly relevant as China expands its influence into its near abroad, thereby disrupting global power distributions. Although China's desire to assert control in the heart of Eurasia may not always involve outright territorial conquest (Callahan, 2008; Cannon and Rossiter, 2025), Beijing's integration into the region's technological and economic ecosystems produces a similar effect (Lupion, 2021; Sim and Aminjonov, 2024; Cannon, Sim and Aminjonov, 2025). This expansion has prompted Eurasia's rimland states to coordinate security architectures once viewed as distinct – namely, those of the Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific (Grgić and Wilkins, 2025; Cannon, 2025).

This confluence of his Midland Ocean which constituted, according to Mackinder, 'a bridgehead in France, a moated aerodrome in Britain, and a reserve of trained manpower, agriculture and industries in the Eastern United States and Canada' with the outer crescent of states stretching across the 'Monsoon Lands' of India through Southeast Asia to Japan is a fulfilment of the great geographer's thoughts laid out between 1904 and 1942, when he published his final work, *The Round World and the Winning of the Peace*. Indeed, Mackinder realized the import of his original Heartland theory from the vantage point of history towards the end of his life, having witnessed the prospect of Germany winning the First World War. This would have, Mackinder surmised, allowed Berlin to establish '... sea-power on a wider base than any in history, and in fact on the widest possible base' (Mackinder, 1919, p.106).

China's Belt and Road Initiative and the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation serve as political-economic tools to extend influence and embed Beijing in the infrastructure, technologies, and operations of Central and broader Eurasia (Rozman, 2010; Xie, 2021). China's territorial demands underscore how geography shapes state power – particularly at

geostrategic nodes such as the Himalaya, Central Asia, and littoral regions near chokepoints (Panda, 2024; Cannon, 2024).

Mackinder recognized that technological advances (in his day, railways) can drastically expand a state's reach within Eurasia. Today, China's high-speed rail lines, pipelines, and digital infrastructure (e.g. 5G networks) similarly bind Eurasia's Heartland to global markets and augment Beijing's political-economic leverage. Yet, as Mackinder (1904; 1919; 1942) would remind us, technology alone does not confer dominance unless paired with a near-autarkic resource base. China still imports the bulk of its hydrocarbons by sea, whereas Russia wields abundant oil and gas but lacks diversified metals and high-tech inputs. China's crude-oil import dependence stood at over 70 per cent prior to the pandemic (Global Times, 2019). This asymmetry highlights Mackinder's warning: mobility matters only when backed by ample territorial resources. Beijing's quest for rail and pipeline corridors across Central Eurasia aims less at speed than at securing inland hydrocarbon flows that would reduce its Persian Gulf vulnerability – classic Mackinder strategy of converting continental resources into strategic freedom of action.

Likewise, modern capabilities – cyber, advanced air power, and space assets – test older notions of geographic determinism but do not negate them. Conflicts in Ukraine and elsewhere show that air and cyber campaigns alone cannot secure victory without control of the ground. Even next-generation infrastructures depend on undersea communication cables, server farms, and satellites, all of which retain a territorial component.

China's advances have drawn Eurasia's rimland states closer together. India – proud of its non-alignment status – has grown closer to the U.S., Japan, Australia, France, and the E.U. in response to Beijing's assertiveness (Panda, 2024). Similarly, Vietnam's concerns over Chinese activities have increased its security engagement with the United States and Japan. The Philippines has pushed back against China's maritime pressures by hosting more American military personnel than at any time since the Cold War (De Castro, 2024). Over the past decade, Japan has evolved from a primarily economic actor to a major political and security player, reforming its defence doctrine, boosting defence spending, and championing a 'free and open Indo-Pacific' (Hakata, Aizawa and Cannon, 2024). France's strategic presence and overseas territories in the Indian and Pacific Oceans further highlight its commitment to constraining Chinese expansion (Duggal, 2022).

Meanwhile, in Western Eurasia, Russia's 2022 invasion of Ukraine jolted Europe out of its post-Cold War assumption that non-traditional threats had eclipsed conventional security concerns. Confronting two decades of Russian political interference, European states moved closer to their historic offshore balancer – the U.S. – increasing defence budgets, expanding NATO, and designating Russia as their chief threat (with China viewed as a major strategic competitor).

Against this backdrop, rimland states such as India, Japan, South Korea, France, and the U.K. have become pivotal players in countering Eurasian hegemony. The Quad – comprising India, Japan, the U.S., and Australia – exemplifies a shared effort to uphold a free and open Indo-Pacific and a rules-based order (Cannon and Rossiter, 2022). Established in 2007 and revived in 2017, this informal minilateral cemented the Indo-Pacific concept and served as a precursor to the emerging latticework of security architecture linking the Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific (Grgić, 2024). This networked architecture also resonates with Mackinder’s (1919) notion of an ‘outer rampart’ of sea-power states such as the U.S. and Japan coupled with the United Kingdom, France, and Australia. The impetus behind these developments reflects Mackinder’s prediction that states on Eurasia’s periphery would seek to curb the ambitions of dominant Heartland powers.

Some might counter that Eurasian powers are simply repelling the global reach of a dominant U.S., whose hub-and-spoke alliance system extends into their near abroad. Yet neither China nor Russia aims to seize American territory; both remain primarily focused on controlling or influencing adjacent regions. As Mackinder noted, the ‘secular struggle’ (1904) to dominate parts of Eurasia tends to galvanize peripheral states into collective resistance.

Yet, why would Germany or France care about China’s claims in the South China Sea, and why does Japan so emphatically support Ukraine against Russia? Mackinder explained it in terms of the balance of power:

The oversetting of the balance of power in favour of the pivot state, resulting in its expansion over the marginal lands of Euro-Asia, would permit the use of vast continental resources for fleet-building, and the empire of the world would then be in sight.

(Mackinder, 1904, p.436).

Writing on the eve of the Second World War, another great geopolitical theorist, Spykman (1944) expanded on this idea, arguing that a true hegemon in central Eurasia would unite Eurasian rimland states such as Britain, Japan, and the U.S. For his part, Mackinder envisioned:

France, Italy, Egypt, India, and Corea [Korea] would become so many bridgeheads where the outside navies would support armies to compel the pivot allies to deploy land forces and prevent them from concentrating their whole strength on fleets.

(Mackinder, 1904, p.436).

This sums up his geopolitical theory: the possibility of a Eurasian hegemon inspires cooperative balancing among otherwise separate actors, thereby shaping the global balance of power. Present-day alliances and security architecture, aimed at limiting China’s and

Russia's influence, uphold Mackinder's vision and illustrate his enduring relevance (Grgić and Wilkins, 2025; Cannon, 2025).

The cork in the bottle and geostrategy

Regardless of how one feels about Mackinder's privileging of Eurasia, states around and beyond the Eurasian landmass can also shape global power dynamics significantly by either enabling or restricting maritime access. This is because some island states and peninsulas occupy strategic geographies and hold what might be termed a 'cork in the bottle' position, allowing them to bottle up a potential hegemon. Taiwan's independence and sovereignty, for example, constrain China's ambitions in the Western Pacific by preventing Beijing from unfettered maritime expansion. India's control over the Andaman and Nicobar Islands likewise provides formidable leverage in the Bay of Bengal, helping Delhi oversee critical sea lanes of communication connecting the Strait of Malacca to the Indian Ocean. Diego Garcia, which has been held jointly by the U.K. and U.S., grants Washington unprecedented capacity to project power across the broader Indian Ocean. Seychelles, despite its small size, could assume an analogous role if its ports or airfields are used to monitor or interdict naval movement.

Historically, Malta in the central Mediterranean exemplifies the importance of such nodes. During the Second World War, it remained unconquered by Axis forces, enabling Britain – along with its control of Gibraltar to the west and the Suez Canal to the east – to resupply, coordinate forces, and ultimately gain the upper hand in that theatre (Hanson, 2017). In Mackinder's terms, these islands, peninsulas, and chokepoints reinforce the constraints that inner and outer crescent states can impose on a would-be Eurasian hegemon.

When taken together – Taiwan, Seychelles, Malta, Diego Garcia, and others – these geostrategic positions can effectively contain or bottle up a revisionist power by denying it full access to the broader maritime commons. Depending on their calculus, small island states can choose to cooperate with Eurasian rimland states to impede the expansion of Heartland-based challengers, thereby affecting distributions of power on a global scale.

Conclusion

Halford Mackinder's insights, forged over a century ago, remain foundational to understanding the enduring architecture of global power. Far from being eclipsed by technological advance or economic interdependence, his recognition of the centrality of geography – of strategic territory, resources, and how technology can overcome it – has only

gained salience in an era of resurgent great power rivalry. The gravitational pull of Eurasia persists: China's integration into Central Asia, Russia's re-assertion in Eastern Europe, and the knitting together of Euro-Atlantic and Indo-Pacific security architectures all reaffirm Mackinder's core premises.

Contemporary technologies – railways in Mackinder's time, cyber and satellites today – amplify reach but do not negate the decisive importance of strategic geography. Nor do the security formations such as the Quad transcend the geographic logic he outlined; they embody it. Rimland states and offshore balancers such as the U.S. are beginning security interactions to balance hegemonic ambitions in Eurasia's Heartland, fulfilling the pattern Mackinder foresaw.

Ultimately, Mackinder's parsimonious vision endures not because it reduces complexity, but because it captures the strategic constants beneath it: geography, power, and resources. In a globalized world increasingly shaped by inter-Eurasian dynamics, his theories remain indispensable for interpreting the structures of power that persist, adapt, and re-emerge.

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